

Table S1. (a) Relative frequency (%) of polyploid homeologs detected in the studied *Triticum* species by our *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm across the aligned core genes and their grafted ranked position (rank) across 100 bootstrap replicates. Only those occurring in more than 10% of the selected genes in each accession (see Table 1a, Homeolog-types) were included in the analysis. Homeologs were classified into nine types ('a' to 'i') according to their grafting positions in the diploid tree. Columns a-i indicate the global percentage of a homeolog-type across 100 random bootstrap replicates from pruned alignments (all diploid orthologs plus the polyploid homeolog), in which the *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm grafted the homeolog in a particular branch. The branch with the highest frequency is underlined and 10% of this value represents the lowest threshold allowed to include additional branches in the distribution of that homeolog-type. Only the most frequent homeologs (indicated with asterisks) were assigned to subgenomes, matching the ploidy level of each studied polyploid species informed by cytogenetic data (Marcussen *et al.*, 2014). **(b)** Frequency of polyploid heterologous copies across genes and subgenomes (homeologous subgenomes inferred according to our *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm) in *Triticum* polyploid species. All the *Triticum* homeologs were assigned to simple subgenomes (containing only one homeolog-type). Heterolog-types' ranked bootstrap values are represented as subgenomic components in Figure S2. **(c)** Pairwise patristic distances between the *Triticum-Aegilops* diploid orthologous branches and the polyploid homeologous subgenomic branches of the consensus ML tree based on 48 nuclear core genes, and 181 orthologous and homeologous sequences. Patristic distances were calculated with Geneious R11.1.5. Abbreviations of accessions correspond to *Triticum urartu* (Tura) (2x, 2n = 14), *T. aestivum* (Taes) (6x, 2n = 42), *T. turgidum* (Ttur) (4x, 2n = 28), *T. monococcum* (Tmon) (2x, 2n = 14), *Aegilops sharonensis* (Asha) (2x, 2n = 14), *Ae. tauschii* (Atau) (2x, 2n = 14) and *Ae. speltooides* (Aspe) (2x, 2n = 14).

(a)

Polyploid accession code	homeolog	% (rank)	10% threshold	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
Ttur	c*	44.97 (1)	9.3	0.5	3.1	<u>92.8</u>	1.8	0.2	1.1	0.3	0	0.1
	i*	41.48 (2)	8.0	0.7	0.6	0	0	0	0	<u>11.9</u>	6.4	<u>80.3</u>
Taes	f*	37.02 (1)	9.6	0	0	0	2.6	1.7	<u>95.6</u>	0	0	0
	c*	27.72 (2)	9.2	0.3	2.8	<u>92.6</u>	2.8	0.4	0.8	0.1	0	0.1
	i*	26.24 (3)	8.3	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	<u>8.4</u>	8.5	<u>82.9</u>

(b)

Polyploid accession code	ploidy	Rank (number) of homeologs across genes and their grafting frequencies in branches [bootstrap distribution in %] according to the <i>Nearest Diploid Species Node</i> algorithm	Inferred subgenomes
Ttur	4x	c = 1 (2878) [c=92.8] i = 2 (2655) [i=80.3]	CI
Taes	6x	c = 2 (3243) [c=92.6] f = 1 (4331) [f=95.6] i = 3 (3070) [i=82.9]	CFI

(c)

	Tura	Taes_i	Ttur_i	Tmon	Asha	Atau	Taes_f	Aspe	Taes_c	Ttur_c
Tura	0									
Taes_i	0.002	0								
Ttur_i	0.003	0.001	0							
Tmon	0.006	0.006	0.006	0						
Asha	0.022	0.022	0.023	0.022	0					
Atau	0.021	0.021	0.022	0.021	0.008	0				
Taes_f	0.021	0.021	0.022	0.021	0.008	0.001	0			
Aspe	0.022	0.022	0.023	0.022	0.017	0.016	0.016	0		
Taes_c	0.022	0.023	0.023	0.023	0.018	0.017	0.017	0.009	0	
Ttur_c	0.023	0.024	0.024	0.024	0.019	0.018	0.018	0.01	0.002	0

References in Table S1.

Marcussen, T., Sandve, S.R., Heier, L., et al. (2014) Ancient hybridizations among the ancestral genomes of bread wheat. *Science* (80-.), 345.

Table S2. List of *Brachypodium* species and ecotypes and outgroup taxa used in the study. Information on locality of origin, accession code, voucher code, genome size (GS), chromosome number ($2n$), chromosome base number (x), inferred ploidy level, life-cycle, and source of transcriptomic, cytogenetic, genomic and comparative chromosome barcoding (CCB) data are provided for each accession. Genome size and chromosome number values obtained in this work are shown in bold. Vouchers are deposited in the JACA (Pyrenean Institute of Ecology-CSIC, Jaca, Spain) and University of Zaragoza (UZ) herbaria.

Taxa	Locality	Accession code (abbreviation in figures)	Voucher code	GS (pg/2C)	$2n$	x	Ploidy	Life-cycle	Source of data
<i>B. arbuscula</i> Gay ex Knoche	Spain: Canary Isles: La Gomera: Vallehermoso	Barb502 (Barb)	JACA R308200	0.713±0.004	18	9	2x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS and CCB (this study), $2n$ (Robertson, 1981)
<i>B. boissieri</i> Nym.	Spain: Granada: Puerto de la Mora, Granada: Dornajo	Bbois3 Bbois10 (Bboi)	JACA R308201 UZ13/17	3.236±0.072	48	8	6x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS, $2n$ and CCB (this study)
<i>B. distachyon</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Iraq: Salah ad Din, 4 km from Salahuddin	Bd21 -SRX1721359 (Bdis)	JACA 298981	0.631	10	5	2x	annual	RNA-seq data (Bettgenhaeuser <i>et al.</i> , 2017), GS and $2n$ (Catalán <i>et al.</i> , 2012).
<i>B. hybridum</i> Catalán, Joch. Müll., Hasterok & Jenkins	Turkey	Bhyb_BdTR6g (Bhyb)	JACA R308209	1.265	30	10+5	4x	annual	RNA-seq (this study), GS and $2n$ (Catalán <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Gordon <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>B. mexicanum</i> (Roem. & Schult.) Link	Mexico: Hidalgo: Sierra de Pachuca	Bmex347 (Bmex)	JACA R308202	3.774±0.033	40	10	4x	short-perennial	RNA-seq and GS (this study), $2n$ (Shi <i>et al.</i> , 1993)
<i>B. phoenicoides</i> (L.) P. Beauv. ex Roem. & Schultes	Slovakia: Ružomberok	Bpho422 (Bpho422)	JACA R308203	1.469±0.012	28	9+5	4x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS and $2n$ (this study)
<i>B. phoenicoides</i> (L.) P. Beauv. ex Roem. & Schultes	Spain: Huesca: Panzano	Bpho6 (Bpho6)	JACA R308204	1.443±0.019	28	9+5	4x	perennial	RNA-seq and GS (this study), $2n$ (Betekhtin <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
<i>B. pinnatum</i> (L.) P. Beauv. (diploid A)	Norway USDA PI 345982	Bpin505 (Bpin)	JACA R308205	0.822±0.009	18	9	2x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS and $2n$ (this study)

<i>B. retusum</i> (Pers.) P. Beauv.	Spain: Huesca: Angües, France: Vic la Gardiole	Bret400 Bret504 (Bret)	JACA R308206 UZ 7475jam	1.704±0.024	32	8+8	4x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS, 2n and CCB (this study)
<i>B. rupestre</i> (Host) Roem. & Schult. (tetraploid)	Spain: Huesca: Jaca: Aratorés: Castiello de Jaca	Brup5 (Brup)	JACA R308207	1.469±0.037	28	9+5	4x	perennial	RNA-seq, GS and 2n (this study)
<i>B. stacei</i> Catalán, Joch. Müll., Mur & Langdon	Spain: Canary Isles: La Gomera: Agulo	Bsta_TE4.3 (Bsta)	JACA R308208	0.564	20	10	2x	annual	RNA-seq (this study), 2n (López-Álvarez <i>et al.</i> , 2012), GS (Catalán <i>et al.</i> , 2012; Gordon <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
<i>B. sylvaticum</i> (Huds.) P. Beauv.	Spain: Ávila	Brasy-Esp F-88 PI318962 (Bsyl)	-	0.844±0.007	18	9	2x	perennial	RNA-seq (Fox <i>et al.</i> , 2013), GS and 2n (Wolny and Hasterok, 2009)
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> subsp. vulgare cv. Morex	-	ERR159679 (Hvul)	-	11.13	14	7	2x	annual	RNA-seq (https://plants.ensembl.org), GS and 2n (Johnston <i>et al.</i> , 1999)
<i>Oryza sativa</i> L. (Japonica group)	-	Nipponbare SRX738077 (Osat)	-	0.91	24	12	2x	annual	RNA-seq (Sun Yat-Sen University), GS and 2n (Uozu <i>et al.</i> , 1997)

References in Table S2.

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Table S3. (a) Total filtered paired-end (PE) and single-end (SE) reads used to build the RNA-seq data set of the *Brachypodium* species, ecotypes and outgroup taxa under study. Newly generated data are indicated in bold. Crosses indicate transcriptome data obtained in other studies. **(b)** Statistics of the assembled transcripts obtained from the *Brachypodium* species and ecotypes under study using Trinity assembler. Genes correspond to Trinity components, while transcripts include all the assembled isoforms. Contig N50 indicates that at least half of all assembled nucleotides are in transcript contigs of at least the detected N50 length value. Sources of accessions are indicated in Table S2.

(a)

Samples	RNA-seq
<i>B.arbuscula</i>	25,461,838
<i>B.boissieri</i>	23,602,582
<i>B.distachyon</i> Bd21†	24,523,648
<i>B.hybridum</i> BdTR6g	13,876,186
<i>B.mexicanum</i>	19,464,557
<i>B.phoenicoides</i> Bpho6	26,550,837
<i>B.phoenicoides</i> Bpho422	22,318,373
<i>B.pinnatum</i>	23,012,037
<i>B.retusum</i>	25,579,987
<i>B.rupestre</i>	20,203,954
<i>B.stacei</i> TE4.3	10,439,505
<i>B.sylvaticum</i> Esp†	50,687,151
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> †	23,922,873 (SE)
<i>Oryza sativa</i> †	33,377,660

(b)

Samples	Total Trinity genes	Total Trinity transcripts	% GC	Stats based on ALL transcript contigs				Stats based on ONLY LONGEST ISOFORM per 'GENE'			
				Contig N50	Median contig length	Average contig length	Total assembled nucleotides	Contig N50	Median contig length	Average contig length	Total assembled nucleotides
<i>B.arbuscula</i>	81,409	124,549	48.41	1,507	555	909.59	113,288,406	1,306	396	741.57	60,370,486
<i>B.boissieri</i>	85,265	132,525	48.85	1,258	483	791.07	104,835,946	1,123	371	676.95	57,720,048
<i>B.hybridum</i>	72,025	102,627	49.73	1,112	430	709.31	72,794,463	980	348	616.78	44,423,843
<i>B.mexicanum</i>	92,817	137,735	49.34	1,121	423	709.82	97,767,065	905	338	594.9	55,217,218
<i>B.phoenicoides</i> Bpho6	108,114	160,417	48.03	1,359	511	842.17	135,098,959	1,190	393	712.14	76,992,275
<i>B.phoenicoides</i> Bpho422	94,758	139,769	48.48	1,310	471	802.07	112,104,432	1,098	356	667.83	63,282,223
<i>B.pinnatum</i>	72,371	108,186	47.94	1,538	552	918.81	99,402,628	1,337	394	747.45	54,093,562
<i>B.retusum</i>	101,941	154,466	48.6	1,217	464	765.63	118,264,125	999	354	631.91	64,418,005
<i>B.rupestre</i>	86,845	119,677	48.81	1,185	414	726.02	86,888,429	989	342	620.08	53,850,943
<i>B.stacei</i>	55,366	72,611	49.31	1,352	469	810.36	58,840,986	1,211	374	702.31	38,883,912

Table S4. (a) Relative frequency (%) of polyploid homeologs detected in the studied *Brachypodium* species by our *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm across the aligned core transcripts and their grafted ranked position (rank) across 100 bootstrap replicates. Only those occurring in more than 10% of the selected genes in each accession (see Table 1b, Homeolog-types) were included in the analysis. Homeologs were classified into nine types ('a' to 'i') according to their grafting positions in the diploid skeleton tree. Columns a-i indicate the global percentage of a homeolog-type across 100 random bootstrap replicates from pruned alignments (all diploid orthologs plus the polyploid homeolog), in which the *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm grafted the homeolog in a particular branch. The branch with the highest frequency is underlined and 10% of this value represents the lowest threshold allowed to include additional branches in the distribution of that homeolog-type. Only the most frequent homeologs (indicated with asterisks) were assigned to subgenomes, matching the ploidy level of each studied polyploid species informed by cytogenetic data (Table S2). **(b)** Frequency of polyploid heterologous copies across genes and subgenomes (homeologous subgenomes inferred according to our '*Subgenome Assignment*' algorithm) in *Brachypodium* polyploid species. The *Brachypodium* homeologs-types were assigned to simple or to compound subgenomes (containing more than one homeolog-type) following the circumscription of bootstrap distribution to contiguous branches [e. g., Bpho422 homeolog-type 'g' showed the highest frequency for its grafted branch 'g' (67.7% BS) but also included the graftings in branches 'f' (8.9% BS), 'h' (8.1%BS), and 'i' (9.4%BS) that were above the 10% threshold, whereas the homeolog-type 'e' only showed a highest frequency grafting to branch 'e' (76.2%BS)]. *Brachypodium* compound subgenome A1 is represented by a+b+c heterolog-types in *B. mexicanum*, A2 by a+b+c+e and a+c in *B. boissieri* and *B. retusum*, respectively, E1 by e+g in *B. retusum*, and G by f+g+h+i in *B. rupestre* and *B. phonicoides*. Homeolog-types' ranked bootstrap values are represented as subgenomic components in Figure S3. **(c)** Pairwise patristic distances between the *Brachypodium* diploid orthologous branches and the polyploid homeologous subgenomic branches of the consensus ML tree based on 322 nuclear core genes, and 1,307 orthologous and homeologous sequences. Patristic distances were calculated with Geneious R11.1.5. Polyploid accession codes and estimated ploidy correspond to those indicated in Table S2.

(a)

Polyploid accession code	homeolog	% (rank)	10% threshold	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
Bpho422	g*	25.4(1)	6.7	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	5.7	<u>8.9</u>	67.7	<u>8.1</u>	<u>9.4</u>
	f	21.0(2)	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	2.8	86.9	8.6	0.8	0.7
	e*	20.6(3)	7.6	0.5	0.8	3.5	4.5	76.2	6.1	5.1	2.4	1.0
	i	15.4(4)	7.2	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	2.7	0.5	<u>11.3</u>	<u>13.0</u>	72.4
	h	15.3(5)	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.4	<u>8.5</u>	80.2	<u>9.8</u>
Bpho6	g*	22.6(1)	7.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	4.3	6.4	70.0	<u>11.1</u>	<u>7.9</u>
	e*	22.4(2)	7.7	0.0	0.1	2.1	3.5	77.0	5.8	6.9	3.4	1.2
	f	21.8(3)	8.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	3.3	88.4	6.3	1.2	0.7
	h	16.4(4)	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.4	6.6	87.0	5.3
	i	15.1(5)	7.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	0.2	<u>9.7</u>	<u>9.5</u>	79.4
Bmex	a*	46.5(1)	8.0	80.2	<u>9.5</u>	<u>8.0</u>	1.1	0.8	0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0
	b	27.2(2)	7.6	<u>8.9</u>	76.6	<u>13.1</u>	1.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	c	23.8(3)	7.1	<u>11.0</u>	<u>13.1</u>	71.5	1.4	1.5	0.1	0.9	0.0	0.4
Brup	g*	27.1(1)	6.9	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	5.4	5.4	69.3	<u>9.5</u>	<u>10.2</u>
	h	22.0(2)	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.9	<u>9.4</u>	80.3	<u>8.4</u>
	e*	18.5(3)	7.5*	0.0	0.0	3.2	3.1	75.4	5.8	<u>8.8*</u>	2.4	1.3
	i	17.7(4)	7.4	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	1.8	0.5	<u>10.3</u>	<u>13.4</u>	73.8
	f	13.3(5)	8.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	84.0	<u>10.3</u>	1.4	0.9
Bret	e*	31.4(1)	7.4	1.4	0.4	5.0	3.8	73.6	5.2	<u>7.2*</u>	2.6	0.7
	c	21.1(2)	7.13*	4.9	6.9	71.3	4.2	<u>7.1*</u>	1.1	2.9	1.1	0.4
	g	18.4(3)	7.3	1.6	0.3	1.0	0.4	5.4	3.7	73.1	<u>7.7</u>	6.8
	a*	15.6(4)	8.0	79.8	4.7	<u>8.2</u>	3.4	1.8	0.2	1.0	0.8	0.0
Bhyb	b*	54.3(1)	9.4	0.7	94.1	4.2	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
	d*	41.0(2)	9.3	0.1	2.1	4.2	93.5	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Bboi	a*	40.6(1)	8.5	85.3	7.9	6.0	0.4	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
	c	23.6(2)	7.4	<u>8.6</u>	<u>9.4</u>	74.4	4.2	3.0	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1
	b	20.9(3)	7.8	<u>8.4</u>	78.5	10.1	1.0	1.7	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
	e	10.7(4)	7.0	1.0	1.5	<u>8.9</u>	<u>11.8</u>	69.9	3.5	1.5	1.0	1.0

(b)

Polyploid accession code	ploidy	Rank (number) of homeologs across genes and their grafting frequencies in branches [bootstrap distribution in %] according to the ‘Nearest Diploid Species Node’ algorithm	Inferred subgenomes
Bboi	6x	a = 1 (6583) [a=85.3] c = 2 (3826) [c=74.4, a=8.6, b=9.4] b = 3 (3381) [b=78.5, a=8.4] e = 4 (1740) [e=69.9, c=8.9, d=11.8]	A2
Bhyb	4x	b = 1 (12058) [b=94.1] d = 2 (9093) [d=93.5]	BD
Bmex	4x	a = 1 (7949) [a=80.2, b=9.5, c=8.0] b = 2 (4646) [b=76.6, c=13.1, a=8.9] c = 3 (4067) [c=71.5, b=13.1, a=11.0]	A1
Bpho6	4x	g = 1 (4620) [g=70, h=11.1, i=7.9] e = 2 (4569) [e=77] f = 3 (4449) [f=88.4] h = 4 (3351) [h=87]	E2G
Bpho422	4x	i = 5 (3090) [i=79.4, g=9.7, h=9.5] g = 1 (4973) [e=67.7, f=8.9, h=8.1, i=9.4] f = 2 (4112) [f=86.9] e = 3 (4046) [e=76.2] i = 4 (3028) [i=72.4, g=11.3, h=13] h = 5 (2992) [h=80.2, g=8.5, i=9.8]	E2G
Bret	4x	e = 1 (4830) [e=73.6] c = 2 (3247) [c=71.3] g = 3 (2826) [g=73.1, h=7.7] a = 4 (2395) [a=73.6, c=8.2]	A2E1
Brup	4x	g = 1 (5360) [g=69.3, h=9.5, i=10.2] h = 2 (4354) [h=80.3, g=9.4, i=8.4] e = 3 (3663) [e=75.4, g=8.8] i = 4 (3512) [i=73.8, g=10.3, h=13.4] f = 5 (2631) [h=84; g=10.3]	E2G

(c)

	Bsta	Bhyb_b	Bmex_b	Bboi_b	Bdis	Bhyb_d	Barb	Brup_f	Bpho6_f	Bpho422_f	Bpin	Brup_i	Bpho422_i	Bpho6_i	Bsyl	Bpho6_h	Bpho422_h	Brup_h	Bpho6_g	Bpho422_g	Brup_g	Bret_g	Bpho6_e	Bpho422_e	Brup_e	Bboi_e	Bret_e	Bboi_c	Bret_c	Bmex_c	Bmex_a	Bboi_a	Bret_a		
Bsta	0																																		
Bhyb_b	0.008	0																																	
Bmex_b	0.031	0.03	0																																
Bboi_b	0.03	0.029	0.024	0																															
Bdis	0.04	0.038	0.039	0.038	0																														
Bhyb_d	0.04	0.038	0.04	0.039	0.005	0																													
Barb	0.038	0.037	0.038	0.037	0.025	0.025	0																												
Brup_f	0.037	0.036	0.037	0.036	0.024	0.024	0.005	0																											
Bpho6_f	0.038	0.036	0.038	0.037	0.024	0.025	0.006	0.003	0																										
Bpho422_f	0.038	0.037	0.038	0.037	0.024	0.025	0.006	0.003	0.002	0																									
Bpin	0.039	0.037	0.038	0.037	0.025	0.025	0.01	0.009	0.01	0.01	0																								
Brup_i	0.04	0.038	0.039	0.038	0.026	0.026	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.011	0.005	0																							
Bpho422_i	0.04	0.038	0.039	0.038	0.026	0.026	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.011	0.005	0.004	0																						
Bpho6_i	0.039	0.038	0.039	0.038	0.026	0.026	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.004	0.004	0.002	0																					
Bsyl	0.039	0.038	0.039	0.038	0.026	0.026	0.011	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0																				
Bpho6_h	0.039	0.038	0.039	0.038	0.026	0.026	0.011	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.004	0																			
Bpho422_h	0.04	0.038	0.04	0.039	0.026	0.026	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.011	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.007	0.005	0.002	0																		
Brup_h	0.039	0.037	0.038	0.037	0.025	0.025	0.01	0.009	0.01	0.01	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.004	0.002	0.003	0																	
Bpho6_g	0.038	0.036	0.037	0.036	0.024	0.024	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.009	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.006	0																
Bpho422_g	0.038	0.037	0.038	0.037	0.024	0.025	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.006	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.008	0.006	0.002	0															
Brup_g	0.037	0.035	0.036	0.035	0.023	0.023	0.008	0.007	0.008	0.008	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.005	0.003	0.003	0														
Bret_g	0.04	0.039	0.04	0.039	0.027	0.027	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.009	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.009	0.008	0.009	0.007	0													
Bpho6_e	0.036	0.035	0.036	0.035	0.023	0.023	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.011	0.01	0.011	0.009	0.013	0												
Bpho422_e	0.037	0.036	0.037	0.036	0.024	0.024	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.011	0.012	0.01	0.014	0.004	0												
Brup_e	0.035	0.034	0.035	0.034	0.022	0.022	0.01	0.009	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.011	0.012	0.01	0.009	0.01	0.008	0.012	0.004	0.005	0											
Bboi_e	0.042	0.04	0.041	0.04	0.028	0.028	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.02	0.021	0.021	0.02	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.02	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.021	0.017	0.018	0.016	0									
Bret_e	0.037	0.035	0.037	0.036	0.023	0.023	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.014	0.015	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.015	0.014	0.014	0.013	0.017	0.013	0.014	0.012	0.012	0								
Bboi_c	0.035	0.034	0.035	0.034	0.029	0.029	0.027	0.026	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.028	0.029	0.028	0.028	0.028	0.029	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.025	0.029	0.025	0.026	0.024	0.03	0.026	0							
Bret_c	0.034	0.032	0.033	0.032	0.027	0.027	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.026	0.027	0.027	0.026	0.026	0.026	0.027	0.026	0.025	0.025	0.024	0.027	0.023	0.024	0.022	0.029	0.024	0.013	0						
Bmex_c	0.036	0.034	0.036	0.035	0.031	0.032	0.03	0.029	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.031	0.031	0.031	0.031	0.031	0.031	0.03	0.029	0.03	0.028	0.032	0.028	0.029	0.027	0.033	0.028	0.027	0.025	0					
Bmex_a	0.042	0.04	0.042	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.04	0.039	0.04	0.04	0.041	0.042	0.042	0.041	0.041	0.041	0.042	0.041	0.04	0.04	0.039	0.042	0.038	0.039	0.037	0.044	0.039	0.037	0.036	0.038	0				
Bboi_a	0.045	0.043	0.044	0.043	0.044	0.045	0.043	0.042	0.043	0.043	0.043	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.043	0.042	0.043	0.041	0.045	0.041	0.042	0.04	0.046	0.041	0.04	0.038	0.041	0.025	0			
Bret_a	0.046	0.044	0.045	0.044	0.045	0.046	0.044	0.043	0.044	0.044	0.044	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.044	0.043	0.044	0.042	0.046	0.042	0.043	0.041	0.047	0.042	0.041	0.039	0.042	0.026	0.015	0		

Table S5. (a) Homeolog allelic and subgenomic data sets of *Brachypodium hybridum* ABR113. Number (#) and percentage (%) of polyploid homeolog alleles that were detected in the encoding genes of the 322 selected transcripts in this allotetraploid reference genome by our *Nearest Diploid Species Node* and *Bootstrapping Refinement* algorithms using orthologous CDS of the available *Brachypodium* diploid reference genomes (*B. stacei* ABR114, *B. distachyon* Bd21, *B. arbuscula* Barb1, *B. sylvaticum* Ain-1). The homeologs were classified into seven homeolog types ('a'; 'b'; 'c'; 'd'; 'e'; 'f' and 'h') according to their grafting positions in the diploid skeleton tree (Figures S4A B, C). The inferred homeologous subgenomes of *B. hybridum* ABR113 were selected and labeled according to the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm. **(b)** Relative frequency (%) of polyploid homeologs detected in allotetraploid *B. hybridum* ABR113 by our *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm across the aligned CDS and their grafted ranked position (rank) across 100 bootstrap replicates. Columns 'a-f' and 'h' indicate the global percentage of a homeolog-type across 100 random bootstrap replicates from pruned alignments (all diploid orthologs plus the polyploid homeolog), in which the *Nearest Diploid Species Node* algorithm grafted the homeolog in a particular branch. The branch with the highest frequency is underlined and 10% of this value represents the lowest threshold allowed to include additional branches in the distribution of that homeolog-type. Only the most frequent homeologs (b, d) were assigned to subgenomes. **(c)** Frequency of polyploid heterologous copies across genes and subgenomes (homeologous subgenomes inferred according to our *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm) in *B. hybridum* ABR113; all its homeologs were assigned to simple subgenomes (containing only one homeolog-type).

(a)

Homeolog type			Inferred Subgenome		
<i>B. hybridum</i> (ABR113)			<i>B. hybridum</i> (ABR113)		
	#	%		#	%
a	-	-	A (a)	-	-
b	87	54.4	B (b)	87	54.4
c	-	-	C (c)	-	-
d	73	45.6	D (d)	73	45.6
e	-	-	E (e)	-	-
f	-	-	F (f)	-	-
h	-	-	H (h)	-	-
Total	160	100	Total	160	100

(b)

Polyploid accession code	homeolog	% (rank)	10% threshold	a	b	c	d	e	f	h
Bhyb (ABR113)	b	54.21 (1)	9.97	0.25	<u>99.70</u>	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	d	45.57 (2)	9.99	0.01	0.00	0.07	<u>99.89</u>	0.03	0.00	0.00

(c)

Polyploid accession code	ploidy	Rank (number) of homeologs across genes and their grafting frequencies in branches [bootstrap distribution in %] according to the <i>Nearest Diploid Species Node</i> algorithm	Inferred subgenomes
Bhyb (ABR113)	4x	b = 1 (8674) [b=99.70] d = 2 (7292) [d=99.89]	BD

Table S6. (a) Theoretical distribution of gene trees obtained from the program COAL under ILS applying Strategy 1. Only gene trees showing a topology congruent with the skeleton diploid species trees were selected. Each column represents the theoretical probabilities (>1%) obtained by grafting homeologous subgenomes ('A', 'B', 'D', 'E1', 'E2', 'G') onto their respective diploid species tree branches ('a+c', 'b', 'd', 'e', 'e', 'g+h') (see Figures 3, 4). Rows indicate the frequency of gene trees with topologies identical to the species tree with the subgenome grafted to that branch. The most frequent COAL gene tree topology is highlighted in gray. Species tree topologies are shown in Table S6c. A(a) and A(c) = Bret_A2; B(b) = Bhyb_B; D(d) = Bhyb_D; E1(e) = Bret_E1; E2(e) = Brup_E2, Bpho6_E2, Bpho422_E2; G(g) = Brup_G, Bpho6_G, Bpho422_G; G(h) = Brup_G represent the subgenomes of the polyploids. Ne is the effective population size (in individuals) for ancestral populations of the tree. Three effective population sizes (Ne= 5E5, 1E6 and 2E6) were tested. **(b)** Relative frequency (%) of observed (Obs) gene tree grafting distribution of homeologs for *Brachypodium* polyploids and theoretical (COAL) distributions according to three effective population sizes (N= 5E5, 1E6 and 2E6) applying the coalescence-based Strategy 1. Theoretical values were obtained by amalgamating in equal proportions the column distributions of Table 1B. Cells with frequencies <10% were excluded. The final values were normalized so that each column totals 100%. Theoretical distributions of grafted subgenomes into branches were amalgamated: E2(e)+G(g) for *B. rupestre* and *B. phoenicoides* Bpho6 and Bpho422; A(a)+E1(e) for *B. retusum*; B (b)+D (d) for *B. hybridum*. In addition, we included the scenarios where *B. rupestre* was formed by E2(e)+G(h) and *B. retusum* by A(c)+E1(e) distributions because of the high observed frequencies of homeolog graftings in branches 'h' and 'c' in these species, respectively. Branches that represent the most likely placement of subgenomes according to the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm are highlighted in color. **(c)** Species trees used to generate homeologous subgenome distributions (columns of Table S6a). Branch lengths are given in coalescence units (CU) = $g/2N_e$, where "g" is the number of generations. Parameters used for COAL were $g=1.5$ years and $N_e=5E5, 1E6$ and $2E6$ individuals. P=*B.pinnatum*, Y=*B.sylvaticum*, A=*B.arbuscula*, D=*B.distachyon*, S=*B.stacei*, O=outgroup, X=polyploid subgenome. Species trees were created from the skeleton diploid tree generated by the standard BEAST analysis (((((P,Y):1.605,A):4.1,D):3.1,S):26.2,O) in My or (((((P,Y):1.07,A):2.73,D):2.07,S):17.4,O) in CU for $N_e=5E5$, (((((P,Y):0.535,A):1.365,D):1.035,S):8.7,O) for $N_e=1E6$ and (((((P,Y):0.268,A):0.683,D):0.518,S):4.35,O) for $N_e=2E6$ by inserting subgenomes in their respective branches. To avoid placing the outgroup within *Brachypodium* we enlarged the stem branch to 17.4 CU. Theoretical probabilities were estimated in each case for the 10,395 topologies that could be computed with 7 tips.

(a)

Effective population size	Branch	A(a)	B(b)	A(c)	D(d)	E1(e)	E2(e)	G(g)	G(h)
Ne=5E5	a	81.4		9.7					
	b	9.3	99.6	9.8					
	c	9.3		62.4		4.3	2.5		
	d			9.1	98.1	4.3	2.5		
	e					65.5	54.8	14.6	6.9
	f					12.5	19.7	15.3	8
	g					12.4	19.2	44.3	13.2
	h							12.3	58.3
	i							12.3	13.2
	Ne=1E6	a	64.7	2.3	14.8	1.1	2.1	1.5	
b		17.5	95	15.5	1.1	2.2	1.6		
c		17.2	2.3	43.5	4.5	9.1	6.6	2.5	1.6
d				13	88.3	9.3	6.8	2.6	1.6
e				12.8	4.5	45.1	39.8	17.6	10.6
f						15.8	21.1	19.9	13.5
g						15.1	19.7	32.2	15.3
h							1.4	12	41.3
i							1.4	12	15.3
Ne=2E6		a	49.4	7.6	18.3	4.3	5.3	4.5	2.6
	b	24.4	81.8	21.3	4.9	6.1	5.1	3	2.1
	c	22.7	7.6	31.1	9	11.4	9.5	5.5	4
	d	1.7	1.5	14.2	69.8	12.4	10.4	6.1	4.4
	e	1.7	1.5	13.3	9	31	28.7	16.1	11.1
	f				1.4	16.1	19.7	19.2	15.1
	g				1.4	14.6	17.2	25.2	14.4
	h					1.6	2.5	11.2	32.5
	i					1.6	2.5	11.2	14.1

(b)

Subgenome Branch	A		B	D	E	G			
	a	c	b	d	e	f	g	h	i
<i>B. rupestre</i> [E2(e)+G(g)]									
Obs					21.2	12.1	29.3	20.2	17.2
5E5					41.3	20.8	37.8		
1E6					38.2	27.3	34.5		
2E6					35.5	30.8	33.6		
<i>B. rupestre</i> [E2(e)+G(h)]									
Obs					21.2	12.1	29.3	20.2	17.2
5E5					34.3	15.4	18	32.4	
1E6					31	21.3	21.5	26.2	
2E6					28.2	24.6	22.4	24.8	
<i>B. phoenicoides</i> 422 [E2(e)+G(g)]									
Obs					23.7	19.6	28.9	12.4	15.5
5E5					41.3	20.8	37.8		
1E6					38.2	27.3	34.5		
2E6					35.5	30.8	33.6		
<i>B. phoenicoides</i> 6 [E2(e)+G(g)]									
Obs					26.3	21.1	24.2	12.6	15.8
5E5					41.3	20.8	37.8		
1E6					38.2	27.3	34.5		
2E6					35.5	30.8	33.6		
<i>B. retusum</i> [A(a)+E1(e)]									
Obs	16.8	24.7			38.4		20.1		
5E5	55.4				44.6				
1E6	42.3	16.7	12.5		28.6				
2E6	36	22.4	20.1		21.5				
<i>B. retusum</i> [A(c)+E1(e)]									
Obs	16.8	24.7			38.4		20.1		
5E5		50.5			49.5				
1E6		39.6		16.8	43.6				
2E6	14.4	25.9	16.7	16.2	26.9				
<i>B. hybridum</i> [B(b)+D(d)]									
Obs			56.8	43.2					
5E5			50.4	49.6					
1E6			52.1	47.9					

(c)

Effective population size	Branch	Species Tree
Ne=5E5	A(a)	(O,(X,(S,(D,(A,(Y,P):1.1):2.7):2.1):1.3):16.1);
	B(b)	(O,((S,X):5.2,(D,(A,(Y,P):1.1):2.7):2.1):17.4);
	A(c)	(O,(S,(X,(D,(A,(Y,P):1.1):2.7):1.0):1.1):17.4);
	D(d)	(O,(S,((D,X):3.6,(A,(Y,P):1.1):2.7):2.1):17.4);
	E1(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):1.1):0.9):1.8):2.1):17.4);
	E2(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):1.1):0.5):2.2):2.1):17.4);
	G(g)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(X,(Y,P):0.5):0.6):2.7):2.1):17.4);
	G(h)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(P,(Y,X):0.6):0.5):2.7):2.1):17.4);
Ne=1E6	A(a)	(O,(X,(S,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.6):1.4):1.1):0.7):16.1);
	B(b)	(O,((S,X):2.6,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.6):1.4):1.1):17.4);
	A(c)	(O,(S,(X,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.6):1.4):0.5):0.6):17.4);
	D(d)	(O,(S,((D,X):1.8,(A,(Y,P):0.6):1.4):1.1):17.4);
	E1(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):0.6):0.5):0.9):1.1):17.4);
	E2(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):0.6):0.3):1.1):1.1):17.4);
	G(g)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(X,(Y,P):0.3):0.3):1.4):1.1):17.4);
	G(h)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(P,(Y,X):0.3):0.3):1.4):1.1):17.4);
Ne=2E6	A(a)	(O,(X,(S,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.7):0.6):0.4):16.1);
	B(b)	(O,((S,X):1.3,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.7):0.6):17.4);
	A(c)	(O,(S,(X,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.7):0.3):0.3):17.4);
	D(d)	(O,(S,((D,X):0.9,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.7):0.6):17.4);
	E1(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.3):0.5):0.6):17.4);
	E2(e)	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):0.3):0.2):0.6):0.6):17.4);
	G(g)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(X,(Y,P):0.2):0.2):0.7):0.6):17.4);
	G(h)	(O,(S,(D,(A,(P,(Y,X):0.2):0.2):0.7):0.6):17.4);

Table S7. (a) Theoretical distribution of gene trees obtained from the program COAL under ILS applying Strategy 2. Only gene trees showing a topology congruent with the diploid skeleton species trees were selected. Each column represents the theoretical probabilities obtained by grafting hypothetical homeologous subgenomes (ancestral: ‘A’ and ‘B’; intermediate: ‘E’; recent ‘G’) to their respective diploid species tree branches. Rows indicate the frequency of gene trees with topologies identical to the species tree with the subgenomes grafted to that branch. The most frequent COAL gene tree topology is highlighted in gray; this topology agrees with the observed species tree topology. Branch lengths of species trees were set to 1 CU (A1, B1, E1 and G1) or 0.5 CU (A05, B05, E05, G05). **(b)** Relative frequency (%) of theoretical (ILS) gene tree grafting distribution of homeologs for hypothetical polyploids A+B, A+E and E+G. ILS values were obtained by amalgamating in equal proportions the column distributions of Table S7a. Cells with frequencies < 10% were excluded. The final values were normalized so that each column totals 100%. Polyploid subgenomes recovered by the *Subgenome Assignment* algorithm are highlighted in dark gray; they correspond to the expected gene tree topology. **(c)** Species trees used to generate homeologous subgenome distributions (columns) of Table S7a. Branch lengths are given in coalescence units (CU) = $g/2N_e$, where “g” is the number of generations and N_e is the effective population size. P= *B.pinnatum*, Y= *B.sylvaticum*, A= *B.arbuscula*, D= *B.distachyon*, S= *B.stacei*, O= outgroup, X= polyploid subgenome. Theoretical probabilities were estimated in each case for the 10,395 topologies that could be computed with 7 tips.

(a)

Branch	A1	A05	B1	B05	E1	E05	G1	G05
a	73.4	52.7	11.2	16.0	2.4	6.5		2.9
b	13.2	22.9	75.5	59.5	2.5	7.6		3.4
c	13.1	21.3	11.2	16.0	9.1	12.1	2.1	5.2
d		1.6	1.1	4.1	9.2	12.8	2.2	5.9
e		1.6	1.1	3.9	58.8	37.3	9.1	11.6
f					9	11.6	9.1	12.2
g					8.9	11.1	59.8	39
h							8.3	9.9
i							8.3	9.9

(b)

Branch	A1+B1 % coalescence	A05+B05 % coalescence	A1+E1 % coalescence	A05+E05 % coalescence	E1+G1 % coalescence	E05+G05 % coalescence
a	42.3	34.4	37.9	29.6		
b	44.4	41.2		15.3		
c	12.2	18.7	11.1	16.7		
d						
e			29.4	19.5	34.0	24.5
f						11.9
g					35.44	25.1
h						
i						

(c)

Subgenome	Species Tree
A1	(O,(X,(S,(D,(A,(Y,P):1.0):1.0):1.0):10.0);
A05	(O,(X,(S,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.5):0.5):0.5):10.0);
B1	(O,((S,X):1.0,(D,(A,(Y,P):1.0):1.0):10.0);
B05	(O,((S,X):0.5,(D,(A,(Y,P):0.5):0.5):10.0);
E1	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):1.0):1.0):1.0):10.0);
E05	(O,(S,(D,(X,(A,(Y,P):0.5):0.5):0.5):10.0);
G1	(O,(S,(D,(A,(X,(Y,P):1.0):1.0):1.0):10.0);
G05	(O,(S,(D,(A,(X,(Y,P):0.5):0.5):0.5):10.0);

Table S8. BAC clones used for the comparative chromosomes barcoding analysis.

BAC name	BAC clone identifier*	Position in the genome (bp)
CEN	BD_CBa0033J12	-
Bd1S/1	BD_CBa0027N17	Bd1: 560624 : 710332
Bd1S/2	BD_CBa0030L10	Bd1: 8680898 : 8845282
Bd1S/3	BD_ABa0020A04	Bd1: 15092918 : 15238493
Bd1S/4	BD_CBa0022H13	Bd1: 23114454 : 23242441
Bd1S/5	BD_ABa0018O15	Bd1: 25727688 : 25878318
Bd1S/6	BD_ABa0044I06	Bd1: 28135872 : 28292480
Bd1S/7	BD_ABa0036J15	Bd1: 31222238 : 31387974
Bd1L/8	BD_CBa0025P22	Bd1: 46564769 : 46692954
Bd1L/9	BD_CBa0044L08	Bd1: 48612347 : 48783561
Bd1L/10	BD_CBa0035K24	Bd1: 51720482 : 51914140
Bd1L/11	BD_ABa0046G17	Bd1: 54082210 : 54253048
Bd1L/12	BD_CBa0028P17	Bd1: 57093738 : 57225377
Bd1L/13	BD_ABa0013D23	Bd1: 64120769 : 64297730
Bd1L/14	BD_ABa0043A05	Bd1: 68898017 : 69053532
Bd2S/1	BD_ABa0027K15	Bd2: 1864643 : 2004976
Bd2S/2	BD_ABa0005E09	Bd2: 10380990 : 10507985
Bd2L/3	BD_ABa0044D02	Bd2: 14006553 : 14195269
Bd2L/4	BD_CBa0022I07	Bd2: 38509106 : 38646001
Bd2L/5	BD_CBa0031I09	Bd2: 46500135 : 46639653
Bd2L/6	BD_CBa0036G07	Bd2: 53816466 : 54010118
Bd3S/1	BD_CBa0028O16	Bd3: 856255 : 1007650
Bd3S/2	BD_ABa0029A17	Bd3: 7006740: 7159041
Bd3S/3	BD_CBa0016A22	Bd3: 11505050 : 11712720
Bd3S/4	BD_ABa0022G01	Bd3: 16038657 : 16055486
Bd3S/5	BD_ABa0033D16	Bd3: 22106200 : 22299788
Bd3L/6	BD_CBa0011M04	Bd3: 36854229 : 37002472
Bd3L/7	BD_ABa0038N13	Bd3: 44001051 : 44142538
Bd3L/8	BD_ABa0026M18	Bd3: 49347850 : 49503810
Bd3L/9	BD_ABa0037C10	Bd3: 52501229 : 52687354
Bd3L/10	BD_ABa0020N10	Bd3: 57504387 : 57653389

BAC name	BAC clone identifier*	Position in the genome (bp)
Bd4S/1	BD_CBa0030B12	Bd4: 2007584 : 2157984
Bd4S/2	BD_ABa0021K11	Bd4: 5356098: 5506730
Bd4S/3	BD_CBa0040J03	Bd4: 7830905 : 8001843
Bd4S/4	BD_CBa0021B09	Bd4: 9502901 : 9667864
Bd4S/5	BD_ABa0010I18	Bd4: 14002249 : 14164264
Bd4L/6	BD_ABa0006J17	Bd4: 29358544 : 29516826
Bd4L/7	BD_ABa0020D08	Bd4: 32504625 : 32642850
Bd4L/8	BD_CBa0035E05	Bd4: 39350118 : 39526113
Bd4L/9	BD_CBa0038H23	Bd4: 42789149 : 43003220
Bd4L/10	BD_ABa0024E12	Bd4: 48004859 : 48154124
Bd5S/1	BD_ABa0019O20	Bd5: 1091367 : 1236179
Bd5L/2	BD_CBa0024J19	Bd5: 20845837 : 21003148

* More detail can be found in the NCBI database under the following URLs: <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clone/library/genomic/424> (BD_ABa library) and <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clone/library/genomic/426/> (BD_CBa library).